

Study of thermodynamic parameters in electrochemical reduction of *N,N'*-(di-benzylidene)-*p*-phenylenediamine

T. V. D. Prasad Rao*, P. Yadagiri Swamy and G. Veerabhadram

Department of Chemistry, University College of Science, Osmania University, Hyderabad-500 007, India

E-mail : theeda_prasad@yahoo.com

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Abstract : The thermodynamic parameters $k_{f,h}^0$, ΔG , ΔH_p , ΔH_v and ΔS are calculated in the electrochemical reduction of *N,N'*-(di-benzylidene)-*p*-phenylenediamine in the pH range from 7.48 to 12.0 at 30 to 60 °C. In evaluation of thermodynamic parameters various treatments are employed. The diffusion current (i_d) is found to increase and half-wave potentials ($E_{1/2}$) shift to more positive values with increase in temperature. The reduction of di-Schiff base is found to be diffusion-controlled and irreversible. The irreversibility found to decrease with the rise in temperature. The solvation phenomenon is predicted on the basis of decrease in value of radius calculated using Stokes-Einstein relation.

Keywords : Thermodynamic parameters, di-Schiff base, diffusion current.

In continuation of our earlier report¹, an attempt has been made to determine the nature of the waves, formal rate constants and other thermodynamic functions of *N,N'*-(di-benzylidene)-*p*-phenylenediamine in the pH range 7.48 to 12.0 with buffers at different temperatures from 30 to 60 °C. In the evaluation of formal rate constants and other thermodynamic functions various methods are employed to verify the usefulness of these methods². Thermodynamic parameters, enthalpy of activation (ΔH_p), transfer coefficient (α) and diffusion coefficients (D) are determined in order to throw some light on the size of the reduced species of di-Schiff base.

Results and discussion

The temperature coefficients values (Table 1) of the diffusion current (i_d) are found to lie in the range from 0.86 to 0.35% per degree³. This is in agreement with earlier values³. The plots of i_d vs $h^{1/2}$ in electrochemical reduction of *N,N'*-(di-benzylidene)-*p*-phenylenediamine in various buffer solutions of pH ranging from 7.48 to 12.0 and at various temperatures from 30 to 60 °C are found to be linear and passing through the origin. Both these results indicating the diffusion-controlled nature of the limiting current.

The diffusion current (i_d) is found to increase with the increase in temperature due to increase in the rate of

Table 1. Effect of temperature on electrochemical reduction of *N,N'*-(di-benzylidene)-*p*-phenylenediamine at different pH values

Temp. (°C)	$-E_{1/2}(A)$ (V)	$-E_{1/2}(B)$ (V)	i_d (μA)	TC (%deg ⁻¹)	ω_a	r (A)	$-E_{1/2}(A)$ (V)	$-E_{1/2}(B)$ (V)	i_d (μA)	TC (%deg ⁻¹)	ω_a	r (A)
pH = 7.48						pH = 8.95						
30	1.465	1.473	9.86	----	0.807	5.04	1.490	1.495	9.35	----	0.797	5.61
40	1.418	1.447	10.75	0.86	0.818	4.24	1.430	1.452	10.14	0.81	0.808	4.77
50	1.385	1.431	11.45	0.63	0.825	3.74	1.405	1.426	10.78	0.61	0.815	4.22
60	1.362	1.401	11.96	0.44	0.831	3.43	1.383	1.407	11.25	0.42	0.821	3.87
pH = 9.51						pH = 10.46						
30	1.500	1.507	8.43	----	0.791	6.90	1.520	1.523	7.30	----	0.784	9.20
40	1.445	1.487	9.13	0.79	0.802	5.88	1.495	1.506	7.88	0.76	0.795	7.89
50	1.419	1.432	9.69	0.59	0.810	5.22	1.479	1.483	8.35	0.58	0.803	7.03
60	1.396	1.405	10.07	0.38	0.815	4.83	1.466	1.475	8.67	0.35	0.809	6.52

where, $E_{1/2}(A)$ is half-wave potential from traditional log plots, $E_{1/2}(B)$ is from Oldham-Parry log plots and TC is temperature coefficient.

protonation of two azomethine groups (-HC=N-) present in di-Schiff base. The half-wave potentials ($E_{1/2}$) are found to shift to more positive values with increase in temperature indicating that lower reduction potentials are needed for consumption of protons with the rise in temperature in electroreduction of di-Schiff base.

The kinetic parameters for the electrode reaction have been calculated using various treatments² (Table 2). The equation deduced for a totally irreversible wave at 30 °C is given by Meites and Israel

$$E_{d.e.} = \frac{0.0615}{\alpha n_a} \log \frac{1.349 k_{f,h}^0 t^{1/2}}{D^{1/2}} - \frac{0.0551}{\alpha n_a} \log \frac{i}{(i_d - i)} \quad (1)$$

which may also be written as

$$E_{d.e.} = E_{1/2} - \frac{0.0551}{\alpha n_a} \log \frac{i}{(i_d - i)} \quad (2)$$

$$\text{where, } E_{1/2} = \frac{0.0615}{\alpha n_a} \log \frac{1.349 k_{f,h}^0 t^{1/2}}{D^{1/2}} \quad (3)$$

where $k_{f,h}^0$ is heterogeneous forward rate constant for the forward reaction (cm s^{-1}) and D is diffusion coefficient ($\text{cm}^2 \text{s}^{-1}$) calculated from the Stokes-Einstein equation at 30 °C⁴.

Koutecky has expressed instantaneous current in the form of $F(X)$, where $F(X)$ is (i/i_d) , and proposed following equation for $k_{f,h}^0$

$$k_{f,h} = k_{f,h}^0 \exp(-\alpha n_a FE/RT) \quad (4)$$

A plot of $\log k_{f,h}$ vs E is a straight line with a slope of $(\alpha n_a F/2.303 RT)$. In present case extrapolation of the plot to the potential SCE, yields $k_{f,h}^0$ value. The effect of spherical diffusion to the dropping mercury electrode can be considered by introducing the correction of $H(X)$ to the above $F(X)$. The values of functions $F(X)$ and $H(X)$ are tabulated by Koutecky and Cizek.

Polarographic curves of irreversible process are analysed yet in another way to obtain kinetic parameters of the electrode reaction and deduced the following relationship by Oldham-Parry

$$E_{1/2} = E_T + \frac{0.0615}{\alpha n_a} \log \frac{1.35 k_{f,h}^0 t^{1/2}}{D^{1/2}} \quad (5)$$

where $k_{f,h}^0$ is the formal rate constant at some convenient reference potential of E_T . From this equation $k_{f,h}^0$ value can be obtained. The Koutecky's treatment for an irreversible wave has been extended by Gaur and

Bhargava. They considered the diffusion to the electrode surface is spherical and not a linear process as assumed earlier. They deduced the following relationship.

$$E_{d.e.} = E_{1/2} - \frac{0.0579}{\alpha n_a} \log \frac{i}{(i_d - i)} \text{ at } 30 \text{ }^\circ\text{C} \quad (6)$$

$$\text{where, } E_{1/2} = \frac{0.0615}{\alpha n_a} \log \frac{k_{f,h}^0 t^{1/2}}{1.128 D^{1/2}} \text{ at } 30 \text{ }^\circ\text{C} \quad (7)$$

The enthalpy of activation (ΔH_p) is calculated from the slope of $\log k_{f,h}^0$ vs $1/T$ plots using the equation, $\Delta H_p = -2.303 \times \text{slope}$. The heat of activation at constant volume (ΔH_v) is evaluated using the relation, $\Delta H_p = \Delta H_v + RT$. The activation free energy change (ΔG) is determined using the relationship, $k_{f,h}^0 = (kT/h) r_o \exp(\Delta G/RT)$, where k is Boltzman constant, h is Plank's constant, ΔG is activation free energy and r_o is mean distance between two depolarizer ions in the bulk solution (2×10^{-8} cm). The activation entropy (ΔS) is calculated using Helmholtz relation, $\Delta S = (\Delta H_v - \Delta G)/T$.

The half-wave potential ($E_{1/2}$) values deduced from the traditional and Oldham-Parry log plots are comparable (Table 1). The slope value of traditional and Oldham-Parry linear log plots at all temperatures found to be greater than expected for a reversible wave, indicating the irreversible nature of the polarographic wave. This is further conformed by the αn_a values determined from the slopes of $\log k_{f,h}$ vs E plots in various treatments. These are also within the range of the values derived from traditional log plots. The αn_a values (Table 1) are found to increase with increase in temperature. This increase in αn_a values is attributed to sole increase in the value of ' α ' (transfer coefficient)⁵. In other words, the irreversibility of electrode reaction decreases with rise in temperature.

In each treatment, the values of $k_{f,h}^0$ are found to increase with rise in temperature, suggesting there by the decrease in the irreversibility. The $k_{f,h}^0$ values calculated using various treatments have shown similar trend, strengthening the validity of results obtained. Further the values of $k_{f,h}^0$ determined by Koutecky-Cizek treatment are almost in agreement with the values derived from Oldham-Parry. This may be due to the reason that while placing the suitable criteria for reversibility and total irreversibility, Oldham-Parry might have considered curvature effect resulting from electrode sphericity as considered by Koutecky-Cizek in introducing correction factor to Koutecky-Weber equation and the influence of double layer structure on electrode kinetics. However,

Note

Table 2. Thermodynamic parameters $k_{f,h}^{\circ}$ (cm s⁻¹), ΔH_p (kcal mol⁻¹), ΔH_v (kcal mol⁻¹), ΔG (kcal mol⁻¹) and ΔS (e. u.) of *N,N'*-(di-benzylidene)-*p*-phenylenediamine in various treatments at various pH and temperatures

Parameters	pH = 7.48				pH = 8.95				pH = 9.51				pH = 10.46			
	30 °C	40 °C	50 °C	60 °C	30 °C	40 °C	50 °C	60 °C	30 °C	40 °C	50 °C	60 °C	30 °C	40 °C	50 °C	60 °C
Meites-Israel																
$k_{f,h}^{\circ} \times 10^{20}$	2.69	7.46	15.21	36.15	2.07	5.03	14.98	27.55	1.96	4.80	11.58	25.78	1.52	2.59	9.67	15.26
ΔH_p	←	17.24		→	←	17.09		→	←	16.93		→	←	16.46		→
ΔH_v	16.60	16.58	16.56	16.53	16.49	16.47	16.43	16.41	16.33	16.31	16.29	16.27	16.06	16.84	11.02	11.89
ΔG	34.21	34.72	35.39	35.99	34.36	34.97	35.60	36.12	34.40	34.99	35.59	36.26	34.55	35.38	36.25	36.84
$-\Delta S$	58.36	58.52	58.63	58.73	59.38	59.57	59.75	59.86	60.12	60.17	60.21	60.48	62.02	62.24	62.46	62.80
Kouteckey-Cizek																
$k_{f,h}^{\circ} \times 10^{20}$	1.31	4.14	9.95	18.53	1.56	4.93	9.24	15.27	1.38	4.89	9.42	15.56	1.17	7.85	8.18	13.78
ΔH_p	←	15.27		→	←	15.09		→	←	14.96		→	←	11.62		→
ΔH_v	15.21	15.19	15.27	15.24	15.25	15.22	15.20	15.17	15.18	15.16	15.14	15.12	15.14	15.12	15.09	15.06
ΔG	34.46	35.01	35.86	36.08	34.51	35.12	35.83	36.45	34.53	35.18	35.84	36.61	34.67	35.72	36.71	37.63
$-\Delta S$	64.31	64.63	64.80	64.97	64.46	64.78	65.07	65.45	64.39	64.55	64.72	64.94	64.86	64.93	65.08	65.22
Oldham-Parry																
$k_{f,h}^{\circ} \times 10^{20}$	1.55	3.94	9.65	17.59	1.32	4.65	8.80	14.56	1.31	4.18	8.61	14.63	1.09	7.22	8.02	13.69
ΔH_p	←	15.93		→	←	15.89		→	←	15.96		→	←	15.62		→
ΔH_v	15.33	15.31	15.29	15.27	15.29	15.27	15.25	15.23	15.28	15.26	15.24	15.22	15.21	15.19	15.16	15.13
ΔG	34.54	35.21	35.90	36.61	34.63	35.28	35.94	36.64	34.61	35.25	35.91	36.70	34.75	35.85	36.83	37.86
$-\Delta S$	63.80	64.01	64.31	64.57	64.26	64.45	64.56	64.77	63.89	64.06	64.17	64.69	78.86	80.05	80.68	81.43
Gaur-Bhargava																
$k_{f,h}^{\circ} \times 10^{20}$	4.09	11.36	29.26	55.04	3.15	12.23	24.34	41.95	2.99	7.62	22.19	39.26	2.32	19.88	24.07	24.97
ΔH_p	←	17.24		→	←	17.44		→	←	17.15		→	←	17.03		→
ΔH_v	16.64	16.62	16.60	16.58	16.84	16.82	16.80	16.78	16.55	16.53	16.51	16.49	16.43	16.41	16.39	16.37
ΔG	33.40	34.46	34.97	35.66	34.11	34.71	35.29	35.94	34.14	34.69	35.35	35.98	34.29	35.31	36.24	37.25
$-\Delta S$	55.66	56.48	57.32	57.72	57.38	57.62	57.69	57.96	58.45	58.51	57.78	58.97	75.96	76.98	77.53	78.30

Oldham-Parry treatment is more preferable than Kouteckey-Cizek treatment in view of its lengthy procedure regarding evaluation and use of standard tables.

The values of other thermodynamic functions viz. ΔH_p , ΔH_v , ΔG and ΔS follow the same trend as that of $k_{f,h}^{\circ}$ with the increase in temperature, further supporting the decrease in the irreversibility of electrode reaction. The positive values of ΔG for all treatments suggests the difficulty in reduction of reducible species, in other words electrode process is non-spontaneous. A little positive increase in the value of ΔG for all treatments with the rise in temperature may be due to inconsistency in the value of r_0 with the change of temperature. The negative values of ΔS obtained in each treatment suggest that the activated state has more rigid structure than the initial state.

Experimental

The *N,N'*-(di-benzylidene)-*p*-phenylenediamine

compound was prepared from *p*-phenylenediamine (Sisco, India) and benzaldehyde (Sisco, India) of A.R. grade, according to reported method⁶. Stock solution of the di-Schiff base (10^{-2} M) was prepared in double-distilled ethanol. The dissolved oxygen from solutions of depolarizer was removed by passing nitrogen gas for about 20 min. The ionic strength was maintained by the addition of required amount of KCl. To suppress the polarographic maxima, Triton-X100 ($5 \times 10^{-4}\%$) was used. The dropping mercury electrode was having characteristics of $m^{2/3}t^{1/6} = 2.39 \text{ mg}^{2/3} \text{ s}^{-1/2}$, was used as a working electrode and SCE as reference electrode. The temperatures of the solutions was obtained with an accuracy of ± 0.2 °C. The polarograms of the di-Schiff base were recorded on polarograph model CLO2 in conjunction with polyflex galvanometer model PL50 supplied by Thoshniwal Instruments, Bombay. The pH meter was a digital model DL-707, supplied by Digisun

Electronics, Hyderabad. The viscosity of the solutions was measured with the Ostwald's viscometer and the values obtained were comparable with the reported values.

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